

Technical note on progress in scenarios and clustering

C3S2_370_MF – Operational production of seasonal forecasts

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1. Executive summary

As part of work package 4 of the C3S2_370_MF contract dedicated to innovative products, Météo-France (MF) has worked on extracting scenarios from the seasonal forecast members (Task 4.1) to refine the analysis of the ensemble forecast beyond the usual operational products (e.g ensemble mean, terciles).

This milestone provides an overview of our progress on this task up to date (January 2023). First, it describes the method we selected to obtain the scenarios. This method relies on a clustering of the members based on the forecast anomalies of near-surface temperature at 2 m (T2M) over Europe. Then, this document also shows how we use composites to analyse the differences between scenarios, not only for the T2M clustering variable but also for total precipitation (PRECIP) and other variables related to atmospheric circulation. We have first implemented this approach to the Météo-France seasonal forecasts, before applying it to five other C3S systems (ECMWF, CMCC, DWD, NCEP and UKMO) and to the multi-system comprising all of those six contributions. This cluster analysis often shows a majority scenario and another minority scenario, which helps to refine the interpretation of the ensemble forecast.

The deepening of this approach, by using other variables and further diagnostics of how scenarios diverge, is to be carried out in the next steps of this task.

2. Introduction

Météo-France routinely issues operational seasonal forecast bulletins on a monthly basis¹. These bulletins target the next season (trimester) and rely on the numerical forecasts provided by the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), including Météo-France's own forecasting system. The forecast bulletin provides information about the upcoming seasonal climate conditions, with a particular focus on temperature and precipitation over Europe and the Mediterranean Basin that consists in synthesis maps built from expert knowledge. For this purpose, the bulletin also includes an outlook on oceanic forcing and large-scale circulation patterns, described as modes of variability (Barnston and Livezey, 1987) and weather regimes (Vautard, 1990).

Each forecast bulletin is evaluated *a posteriori* with its counterpart verification bulletin² that documents the performance of the expertised real-time forecast. The verification bulletins show that the real-world seasonal climate may diverge from the ensemble mean of the seasonal forecasts. Then, is it possible to provide more guidance on the possible outcome by taking more precisely into account the information contained in the ensemble? In line with this question, Task 4.1 in WP4 aims to design coherent scenarios (groups of members) by a clustering approach, to extract and summarize the diversity of possible outcomes beyond the ensemble mean.

1 <http://seasonal.meteo.fr/slides/BulTech>

2 <http://seasonal.meteo.fr/slides/Verification>

The clustering approach presented in this document is based on temperature at 2 m only. Section 3 introduces the data and methodology to define the scenarios. Based on the example of the Météo-France forecast for FMA 2023, Section 4 illustrates the use of composites to compare the seasonal scenarios in terms of surface meteorological parameters (T2M, precipitation), while Section 5 illustrates how these scenarios differ in terms of atmospheric circulation. Next, Section 6 shows a similar extraction of scenarios when clustering is applied to a C3S multi-system ensemble (using a subset of six systems from the C3S data store). Finally, Section 7 summarizes our results and exposes our future plans for the end of Task 4.1.

3. Data and methodology

The clustering approach to extract scenarios has been developed on the numerical seasonal forecasts provided by Météo-France. The data and methodology will be described with this system, for the example of the February-March-April 2023 (FMA 2023) forecasts issued on 1 January 2023.

3.1. Data

The current Météo-France seasonal prediction system (MF System 8) is based on the CNRM-CM coupled climate model (Voldoire et al. 2019) and its output data is stored on a $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ grid with 180 latitudes and 360 longitudes, starting at 89.5°S and 0.5°W and extending northwards and eastwards. The real-time forecasts (e.g FMA 2023 issued January 2023) are made up of 51 ensemble members, while the corresponding re-forecasts consist in 25 ensemble members and cover the 1993-2016 period (e.g FMA 1993 after initialization with 1 January 1993 conditions, and so on). The re-forecasts provide the long-term climatology of the forecasting system for the target season, and are used to compute the real-time forecast seasonal anomalies by subtracting their mean. The climate variables under consideration here are the near-surface temperature at 2 m (T2M), total precipitation (PRECIP) and geopotential height at 500 hPa (Z500).

Besides, we use the forecast modes of variability and Euro-Atlantic weather regimes, as routinely computed by Météo-France for the seasonal forecast bulletin. The modes of variability influencing the European climate are the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO), the East Atlantic mode (EA) and the Scandinavian blocking mode (SCAN). They are calculated by projection of the forecast Z500 anomaly field for FMA 2023 on predefined patterns corresponding to Rotated Principal Components Analysis (Barnston and Livezey, 1987) from the historical ERA-Interim data (Météo-France/DCSC/AVH, 2017a). As for the weather regimes, they are determined for each forecast day in FMA 2023 by taking the daily Sea Level Pressure (SLP) anomaly field and choosing the closest-matching pattern in a set of four predefined weather regimes (Météo-France/DCSC/AVH, 2017b). For wintertime forecasts like FMA 2023, these four possible weather regimes are NAO-, Atlantic Ridge, Blocking and NAO+, and the diagnostic under study is the proportion of each regime in all days within the season.

3.2. Cluster analysis

Cluster analysis (Straus, 2019) is a method used in weather and climate to identify groups of distinct data. This method can be used on numerical simulations and predictions to classify discrete groups of atmospheric states (Nakaegawa and Kanamitsu, 2006). The two main types of clustering algorithms are partitioning (e.g *k-means*, Michelangeli et al. 1995) and hierarchical clustering (Ward, 1963).

Our seasonal scenarios are determined through a hierarchical clustering of the 51 members from the real-time forecasts. This requires a metric to quantify the dissimilarity between two members. Following Nakaegawa and Kanamitsu (2006), the chosen dissimilarity between members i and j is:

$$d_{i,j} = 1 - \text{ACC}(i,j) ,$$

where $\text{ACC}(i,j)$ is the Anomaly Correlation Coefficient between members i and j for T2M over Europe. The corresponding domain is 29.5°W-40.5°E; 30.5°N-70.5°N and grid points corresponding to sea are masked. A grid point is considered to be located at sea if the land-area fraction is less than or equal to 0.5.

The Anomaly Correlation Coefficient is the spatial correlation between the maps of T2M anomalies in members i and j for the FMA 2023 season. Let \mathbf{T}_i and \mathbf{T}_j be the vectors representing the normalized T2M anomaly maps in members i and j . The length of \mathbf{T}_i and \mathbf{T}_j is the number N of land grid points over Europe. \mathbf{T}_i and \mathbf{T}_j are obtained after:

- i) subtracting the reforecast climatology to the T2M maps in members i and j
- ii) dividing the vectors by their own Euclidean norm.

With this definition, $\text{ACC}(i,j)$ is simply expressed as:

$$\text{ACC}(i,j) = \mathbf{T}_i^t \mathbf{T}_j .$$

The 51 x 51 dissimilarity matrix \mathbf{d} between all pairs of members is the starting point of a hierarchical clustering algorithm using Ward's method (Murtagh and Legendre, 2014), as in Nakaegawa and Kanamitsu (2006). The idea behind using $\mathbf{d} = \mathbf{1} - \mathbf{ACC}$ as a dissimilarity matrix is to group the ensemble members according to their spatial patterns of T2M anomalies, as though we were a forecaster considering 51 maps of T2M anomalies and trying to gather those that look similar.

The algorithm starts by considering each member as a separate cluster. Then, it merges two clusters at each step until all members are grouped together into one cluster. The steps of the algorithm can be summarized in a tree-shaped diagram called dendrogram, as in Figure 1b. Depending on the desired number of clusters, we may select any merging step illustrated in the dendrogram.

Figure 1: Explanation of the methodology to determine the seasonal forecast scenarios, illustrated with MF system 8 FMA 2023 forecasts issued January 2023. (a) T2M anomaly maps in the 51 members, relative to the 1993-2016 MF system 8 reforecast climatology, (b) Dendrogram of the 51-member hierarchical clustering (the numbers on the left-hand side represent the inter-class distance factor according to Ward's method).

3.3. How many scenarios?

In this task, the clusters are groups of members representing the seasonal scenarios. The choice of the number of scenarios itself is arbitrary. We therefore decide to rely on two criteria:

- 1) In the interest of concision, we do not allow more than 3 scenarios.
- 2) The optimal number of clusters is based on the largest merging distance in the dendrogram, i.e. whether there is more distance between merging from 3 to 2 clusters, or from 2 to 1.

The application of the clustering algorithm to the FMA 2023 Météo-France seasonal forecasts is illustrated in Figure 1. In agreement with the two criteria above, the number of clusters, and therefore the number of scenarios, is 2. Note that regardless of Criteria 1, which has been added for practical purposes, two clusters is by far the most common optimal number across all our examples (not shown). Note also that an optimal number higher than 3, according to Criteria 2 only, is very uncommon.

For clarity, we will always use the word “scenario” to designate a “cluster” or “group of members” in the rest of this document.

3.4. Composites on scenarios

The clustering algorithm provides labels for each of the 51 members of the seasonal forecast, grouping them into 2 or 3 scenarios. We then perform a composite analysis to describe the climate anomalies as forecast by each scenario, by taking the mean anomalies across all corresponding members. Although the scenarios are obtained from T2M only, this can be applied to any climate variable: the only relevant information is the scenario to which the members belong.

In this note, we will present composites on the original clustering variable T2M and on precipitation over Europe, as diagnostics of the sensible climate forecast by each scenario. In order to investigate the corresponding anomalies of atmospheric circulation, we will also provide composites of Z500 over the Northern Hemisphere, and display the differences in terms of modes of variability and weather regimes.

3.5. Application to a C3S multi-model ensemble

The methodology described above can be applied to any C3S seasonal forecasting system. It can also be applied to a C3S multi-model including all ensemble members from all forecasting systems included. In such a case, the number of members to be clustered into scenarios is not 51, but 304 if the six systems in Table 1 are included. It has extensively been argued that a multi-model leads to a better assessment of the seasonal climate distribution than a single model (e.g. Hagedorn et al 2005): the assumption is therefore that the seasonal scenarios from the C3S multi-model are also more robust. Compared to Section 3.2, an additional technical point with multi-model scenarios is to compute the anomalies of each member using the correct re-forecast climatology, e.g. anomalies in members from DWD must be computed relative to DWD re-forecasts.

System	CMCC	DWD	ECMWF	MF	NCEP	UKMO	Multi-model
Ensemble size	50	50	51	51	52	50	304

Table 1: Ensemble size of the six C3S systems and the multi-model

4. Composites of T2M and precipitation

A first step to describe the scenarios is to show the composites for the original clustering variable, T2M. The T2M composites highlight the main differences in spatial patterns of temperature anomalies over Europe that appear in the ensemble forecast. Based on T2M, we obtain two scenarios for the FMA 2023 Météo-France forecasts. Scenario 1 has 37 members and Scenario 2 has 14 members (see e.g. Figures 1b and 2). Here, the majority scenario forecasts a warm anomaly all over Europe (Figure 2a). The minority scenario exhibits normal to cold conditions over Northern and Eastern Europe and warm conditions over the Mediterranean (Figure 2b). Note also that the oceanic regions are masked as they were not included in the T2M clustering.

Composites on precipitation are meant to show how the discrepancies among members in T2M patterns translate into discrepancies in precipitation patterns. In the FMA 2023 example, we see that the majority scenario is not associated with a strong and consistent large-scale precipitation signal. However, we still notice a positive anomaly over a large part of Northern Europe and over the Alps, and a dry anomaly in the Balkans and around the Black Sea (Figure 2c). The minority scenario (Figure 2d) exhibits a stronger and wetter signal at the European scale, with positive precipitation anomalies on the Iberian peninsula and around the northern Mediterranean, extending up to some locations in western and central Europe.

Figure 2: Composite anomalies of T2M and PRECIP for the members belonging to each of the two scenarios (based on T2M only) in the FMA 2023 forecasts from MF8 issued January 2023. (a) Average T2M anomalies on the majority scenario, (b) Average T2M anomalies on the minority scenario, (c) Average PRECIP anomalies for the majority scenario, (d) Average PRECIP anomalies for the minority scenario. Sea grid points are masked.

5. Analysis of atmospheric circulation

5.1. Composites of Z500

Diagnostics of atmospheric circulation are proposed to provide physical explanations accounting for the scenario patterns of T2M and precipitation. Regarding Z500, the majority scenario (Figure 3a) shows an overall positive anomaly over the northern high latitudes (5-15 m). It also exhibits a strong band of positive anomaly (more than 15 m) over the middle latitudes region. This comes along a patch of negative anomaly over south-eastern Greenland.

In Figure 3b, the minority scenario shows a strong positive Z500 anomaly over the high latitudes (more than 15 m) revealing a strongly positive phase of the Northern Annular Mode. In the meantime, a strong negative anomaly representing a predominantly low-pressure pattern can be seen over the Eastern Atlantic region and extends over western Europe (Iberia, France and Germany). It comes alongside a strong westerly subtropical jet over the Eastern Mediterranean and the Middle East.

Generally speaking, the Z500 composites are most of the time very consistent with the T2M anomalies used for the clustering, and they help explain the major differences between members. In FMA 2023, the peak of positive Z500 anomaly over Russia in the majority scenario accounts for the warm signal by bringing a southerly warm flow to Europe. In the meantime, the negative anomalies in the Eastern Atlantic and the strong Northern Annular Mode are responsible for a cold easterly flow over Northern Europe in the minority scenario.

Figure 3: Composite anomalies of Z500 for the members belonging to each of the two scenarios (based on T2M only) in the FMA 2023 forecasts from MF8 issued January 2023. (a) Average Z500 anomalies for the majority scenario (b) Average Z500 anomalies for the minority scenario.

5.2. Modes of variability and weather regimes

The modes of variability provide additional guidance to investigate the relationships between the atmospheric circulation and the scenarios. Figure 4 shows the scatter plots between modes of variability for each forecast members, as routinely used in the Météo-France seasonal bulletin, but with the additional indication of the corresponding scenario: blue dots belong to the minority scenario, and red dots to the majority scenario.

NAO index vs. SCAN index (Figure 4c) shows that a combination of positive NAO and SCAN mode (top right quadrant) is a strong indicator of the majority scenario, while the minority scenario tends to project on negative NAO. On the contrary, there is no real discrimination between scenarios based on the EA mode (Figure 4d). These results are consistent with the Z500 anomaly maps.

Similarly, it is possible to compare the occurrences of daily weather regimes across the whole season, depending on the scenario. Figure 5 reveals that both scenarios show an excess of days with Blocking relative to the Météo-France reforecast climatology for FMA, and a close to climatological occurrence of Atlantic Ridge. Therefore, the main discriminant feature between the scenarios is the switch between NAO+ and NAO- regimes: while the majority scenario shows a deficit in NAO- and a regular number of NAO+, the minority scenario experiences very few NAO+ and an excess in NAO-. This is in agreement with the cold T2M anomalies in Northern Europe and the wet precipitation anomalies around the Mediterranean that appear in the minority scenario.

Figure 4: Scatter plots between pairs of modes of variability impacting European climate, in the FMA 2023 forecast members from MF8 issued January 2023. The red and blue colours indicate members in the majority and minority scenarios respectively. (a) NAO vs. SCAN modes, (b) NAO vs. EA modes. The T2M anomalies associated to each scenario are provided in (c) and (d) as a reminder.

Figure 5: Histograms of the number of days in the four weather regimes for the months February, March, April and the FMA 2023 season in the MF forecast members belonging to each scenario: (b) Majority scenario (d) Minority scenario. The climatological number of days in the 1993-2016 MF reforecasts is indicated by the background bars. The T2M anomalies associated to each scenario are provided in (a) and (c) as a reminder.

6. C3S multi-model scenarios

The clustering approach is also applied to determine the T2M scenarios in the other C3S models and in the multi-model. This leads to several sets of scenarios, for which the composites of T2M anomalies are provided in Figure 6. Note that in the prospect of using the scenarios for guidance in a seasonal bulletin, a single set of scenarios (e.g multi-model) would be preferable for clarity: the different sets are only shown here for comparison purposes.

Similar to the MF8 forecast described above, the T2M anomalies show mainly two types of scenarios in the individual models for FMA 2023: one majority scenario with a warm anomaly all over Europe and another minority scenario which shows normal to cold conditions over Northern and Eastern Europe. However, NCEP and UKMO show an optimal number of 3 scenarios. This leads to more differences in the minority patterns relative to the other models, while the majority warm scenarios remain broadly consistent. More generally, though the scenarios look similar in all models, some differences can be noted, e.g in the location and the extent of the warmest and coldest anomalies. As for the multi-model ensemble, it shows a majority and a minority scenarios that are very similar to those in Météo-France, both in patterns and in proportion of members. Such a result gives confidence in the robustness of the two scenarios.

Figure 6: Composite anomalies of T2M for the members belonging to the FMA 2023 scenarios in the C3S forecasts issued January 2023: MF, ECMWF, DWD, CMCC, UKMO, NCEP and the multi-model including all of them. Sea grid points are masked.

7. Conclusion and future plans

In this technical note, we propose a methodology to summarize the ensemble seasonal forecasts from C3S into several scenarios of climate anomalies over Europe. This approach relies on a cluster analysis of the ensemble members based on the patterns of T2M anomalies. The clusters of members define scenarios that we represent and analyse using composite maps, not only for the T2M clustering variable but also for other variables (PRECIP, Z500). This cluster analysis often shows a majority scenario and another minority scenario which help us to refine our interpretation of the ensemble forecast.

Most of the diagnostics in this note have been developed on the single Météo-France model due to easier internal data access, but we have also started to work in a multi-model framework to get more robust scenarios. Such multi-model scenarios might be more relevant, e.g for seasonal forecast bulletins that already rely on the C3S multi-model maps. However, their associated diagnostics, for instance composites of variables other than T2M, will require to leverage a larger amount of data.

Finally, our future plans include tests of scenarios with clustering on precipitation or Z500 instead of T2M, as well as a multivariate clustering. The relevance of these other approaches is to be compared to the one presented here. Moreover, we also intend to complement Task 4.1 by designing other diagnostics that will help understand how and why the spread of the ensemble members leads to the scenarios we obtain.

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